

Alkali metal promoted iron-molybdenum oxide as catalysts for anaerobic transformation of cyclohexanol to cyclohexene

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Abstract : Heterogeneous anaerobic transformation of cyclohexanol to cyclohexene is carried out over alkali promoted Fe-Mo oxide catalyst in a solvent-free condition. Various experimental conditions such as temperature, pressure, time and the reuse of catalyst were optimized. Modification of Fe₂O₃-MoO₃ catalyst with alkali metals formed their characteristic phases. Cesium loading resulted in Cs₂FeO₄, Cs_{0.13}MoO₃, Cs_{0.33}MoO₃, Cs₂Mo₇O₂₂ and Cs₂Mo₅O₁₆ phases. The selectivity to cyclohexanone is increased by the use of increasingly complex catalyst system formed due to cesium loading. For the titled transformation, alkali promoted Fe₂O₃-MoO₃ system is recyclable, and behaves as a truly heterogeneous catalyst.

Keywords : Fe₂O₃-MoO₃, cyclohexanol, anaerobic transformation, alkali metal loading, dehydration.

Introduction

Metal oxides including binary and ternary systems have attracted a great attention because of their unique catalytic properties compared with those of individual metal oxides. Such behavior may arise from the interaction between the supported oxide and support, leading to structural and chemical changes¹. The performance of mixed oxide catalysts or metal oxide supported catalysts depends on the structure and textural properties of the catalysts as well as their acid-base nature. The contribution of each of the factors to the catalytic performance depends on the nature of reaction. This acid-base nature of a mixed oxide system can be exploited for transformation of hydrocarbons into precursors for production of fine chemicals^{2,3}. Further development in metal oxide catalyst systems for their effective use for dehydrogenation of various alcohols has been reported in recent studies⁴. Transformation of cyclohexanol to cyclohexanone and cyclohexene is a very useful reaction and has been reported with a number of catalyst systems. Further, this reaction is also used to determine the acidic and basic sites of the catalyst system.

Application of iron, vanadium, molybdenum, etc. in the complex form has been studied towards catalytic oxidation of organic compounds^{5,6}. But the use of Fe₂O₃-MoO₃ catalyst for anaerobic transformations has been reported on rare occasions. To the best of our knowledge, anaerobic transformation of cyclohexanol has not been so far reported over alkali metal promoted Fe₂O₃-MoO₃ catalyst systems. Therefore, it was of interest to explore the possible favorable effect of different calcination temperatures (in the atmosphere of static air) and in the present paper we report the title reaction over alkali metal promoted Fe₂O₃-MoO₃ catalyst. This paper describes the synthesis, characterization and catalytic study of Fe₂O₃-MoO₃ and alkali promoted Fe₂O₃-MoO₃ towards anaerobic transformation of cyclohexanol. The effect of concentration of alkali and acid impregnated binary oxides of Fe and Mo has been studied. Effect of different calcination temperatures on structural changes of the alkali metal promoted catalysts and its impact on conversion and selectivity to prominent products (cyclohexanone and cyclohexene) has also been reported.

Results and discussion

X-Ray diffraction results :

Table 1 presents the XRD data of alkali metal promoted catalysts such as 2θ , d values, phase and corresponding JCPDS file numbers of different samples which are formed by modification of parent $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3$ catalyst as per JCPDS⁷. The predominant phases observed in the calcined alkali, phosphorous and boron promoted and parent $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3$ catalysts are shown in Fig. 1. The parent catalyst ($\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3$) exhibited the phases due to FeMoO_4 and $\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3$ (JCPDS File No. 22-0629 and 20-526 respectively). Formation of $\text{NaFe}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$ phase (JCPDS File No. 30-1195) upon sodium loading was reported in this study. With lithium loading $\text{Li}_2\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3$ and $\text{Li}_3\text{Fe}(\text{MoO}_4)_3$ (JCPDS File No.

72-0780 and 72-0754 respectively) were formed. Cesium loading resulted in Cs_2FeO_4 , $\text{Cs}_{0.13}\text{MoO}_3$, $\text{Cs}_{0.33}\text{MoO}_3$, $\text{Cs}_2\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{22}$ and $\text{Cs}_2\text{Mo}_5\text{O}_{16}$ phases. Thus with cesium loading more complex nature of catalyst surface is formed. But no phase corresponding to Fe-Mo-Cs-O oxide was observed. Phosphorous loading resulted in the formation of new phase $\text{Fe}_2\text{MoP}_{12}$ after calcination. The phase intensity observed at $2\theta = 14.45^\circ$ greatly decreased due to alkali loading.

Spectroscopic data :

In Diffuse Reflectance Ultraviolet-Visible spectrum of $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3$, a band has been observed at 315 nm which may be due to crystalline MoO_3 phase. The bands observed in the range 500–750 nm indicate the presence of Mo in lower oxidation states than 6+.

Table 1. Catalytic performance of different alkali metal promoted catalysts

Catalyst	$\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3$	$\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3\text{-Li}_2\text{O}$ (3 wt%)	$\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3\text{-Na}_2\text{O}$ (3 wt%)	$\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3\text{-K}_2\text{O}$ (3 wt%)	$\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3\text{-Cs}_2\text{O}$ (3 wt%)
%C _{Cyclohexanol}	99.08	90.98	90.96	85.54	83.73
%S _{Cyclohexene}	99.01	96.43	94.77	98.57	98.98
%S _{Cyclohexanone}	0.60	0.88	0.65	0.66	0.64

Reaction temperature = 280 °C, W/F = 86.42 [g_{cat} mol⁻¹_(cyclohexanol h)], Pressure = Ambient.

Fig. 1. XRD profiles of modified $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3$ catalyst : (I) $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3$; (II) $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3\text{-Li}_2\text{O}$ (3 wt%); (III) $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3\text{-Na}_2\text{O}$ (3 wt%); (IV) $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3\text{-Cs}_2\text{O}$ (3 wt%); (V) $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3\text{-P}$ (3 wt%); Calcination temperature : 500 °C.

Therefore, a maximum absorbance observed around 550–600 nm may be due to the presence of Mo^{5+} ion⁸.

Diffuse Reflectance Infrared spectroscopy studies show a broad band in the region 3510–3750 cm^{-1} due to stretching frequency of surface hydroxyl O-H groups⁹⁻¹¹. The bands observed around at ~ 3450 and ~ 1640 cm^{-1} were attributed to molecular water adsorbed on the surface of the oxide. Further, all of the hydroxyl peaks as well as the molecular water bands, around at 1638 cm^{-1} , disappeared at 200 °C.

The IR spectra show shoulder at 900 cm^{-1} which is assignable to $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ stretching¹². The weak band in the range 900–910 cm^{-1} may be assigned to terminal $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ in tetrahedral molybdate species attached to the surface like $(\text{O}_3\text{Mo}=\text{O})^{2-}$. Metal-oxygen stretches generally occur well below 1000 cm^{-1} . Therefore, the peaks observed in the 600–700 cm^{-1} range can be assigned to the formation of new metal-oxy-

gen bonds. The weak and narrow band at 963 cm^{-1} , in all the Fe-Mo-O samples, may be attributed to Fe-O-Mo vibrations.

An additional broad band observed in the range $700\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to the tetrahedral MoO_4 unit in $\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3$. These results indicate that Mo species exist as highly dispersed Fe-O-Mo structures at lower content of Mo and crystallize into the $\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3$ phase at higher content of Mo.

Cyclohexanol transformation :

The product analysis shows that the cyclohexanol transformation associated with formation of cyclohexanone and cyclohexene. Formation of byproducts such as phenol, benzene, cyclohexane, methyl cyclopentene, dicyclohexyl ether and 2-cyclohexylidene cyclohexanone in trace amounts was also observed. The formation of these was confirmed by GCMS (Shimadzu GC-17 A and QP-5000 Mass Spectrometer).

Effect of temperature :

The conversion of cyclohexanol, SRC-ene/C-none (selectivity ratio of cyclohexene to cyclohexanone) (Fig. 2) indicates the dehydration to dehydrogenation activity with variation of reaction temperature at contact time, $W/F = 86.42\text{ g}_{\text{cat}}\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ h}$ and at ambient pressure.

It was observed that as the reaction temperature increases from 180 to $430\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the cyclohexanol conversion also increases linearly from around 23% to nearly complete conversion prevailing cyclohexene selectivity. At a temperature of $430\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ there was no cyclohexanone detected. At higher temperature cyclohexanone formed gets converted into lower cyclic compounds. The selectivity ratio of cyclohexene to cyclohexanone was highest at $430\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ indicating the prominence of cyclohexanol dehydration at higher temperature. The increase in STY is as expected due to high temperature. But at higher temperatures, $380\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and greater, STY decreased due to conversion of liquid hydrocarbons into gaseous products.

Effect of contact time :

The catalytic performance as a variation of contact time is depicted in Fig. 3(a-c). The higher contact time showed a cyclohexanol conversion of 100%

Fig. 2. Catalytic performance of $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3$ catalyst; Effect of reaction temperature on conversion of cyclohexanol and selectivity ratio of cyclohexene to cyclohexanone; Calcination temperature : $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; $W/F : 86.42\text{ g}_{\text{cat}}\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ (cyclohexanol) h}$; Pressure : Ambient.

which is dropped to 95.2% at lower contact time of $43.21\text{ g}_{\text{cat}}\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ (cyclohexanol) h}$. This shows the efficiency of the FeMo catalyst towards cyclohexanol conversion. The cyclohexene selectivity is in direct relationship with contact time of the catalyst. The W/F of $86.42\text{ g}_{\text{cat}}\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ (cyclohexanol) h}$ was taken as an optimum for further investigation of alkali metal promoted catalysts.

Effect of alkali metal loading :

The comparison of cyclohexanol conversion over parent and alkali metal promoted catalysts is illustrated in Fig. 4. A little difference in the conversion was observed over parent and alkali metal promoted catalysts. This indicates that alkali loading does not change the adsorption characteristic of the oxide surface significantly. A comparison at $280\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ where dehydration is prominent as depicted in Table 1 indicates that alkali metal promoted catalysts exhibit improved values of selectivity to cyclohexanone due to cyclohexanol dehydrogenation¹³.

Among the alkali loaded samples, the $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3\text{-Li}_2\text{O}$ showed better performance favoring cyclohexanone formation. It may be noted that similar observation was earlier reported by us including the influence on catalytic performance in oxidation of cyclohexanol¹⁴. Catalysis involves transfer of elec-

Fig. 3. (a-c) : Catalytic performance of $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3$ at varying contact time; (a) Effect of contact time on conversion of cyclohexanol; (b) Effect of contact time on selectivity ratio of cyclohexene to cyclohexanone; (c) Effect of contact time on space-time yield (STY); Calcination temperature : 500 °C; Reaction temperature : 280 °C; Pressure: Ambient.

trons/holes from the surface of the catalyst to the substrate molecule and is reversible. Alkali metal loading reduces the percentage of MoO_3 on the catalyst

Fig. 4. Comparison of parent and alkali metal promoted catalysts at varying temperatures; Calcination temperature : 500 °C; W/F : 86.42 $[\text{g}_{\text{cat}}\text{mol}^{-1}(\text{cyclohexanol})\text{h}]$; Pressure : Ambient.

surface by forming the various phases. Thus available MoO_3 becomes less for the catalytic activity. Since this happens in all the catalyst systems studied, the systems other than $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3$ show nearly similar performance.

Effect of varying amount of Cs_2O loading :

The effects of modification of the catalyst were explored by loading higher percentage of Cs_2O and the results are depicted in Fig. 5. The conversion linearly decreases with loading of Cs_2O at all temperatures except 330 °C and above. However, the cyclohexanone selectivity increased with the amount of loading. The significant rise in selectivity ratio of cyclohexanone to cyclohexene at 180 and 280 °C can be seen in Fig. 6. The rise is prominent at low temperature. The introduction of higher loading of Cs_2O changed the acid-base property of $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3$ catalyst substantially due to complexity in newly formed phases in catalyst. Thus, due to less availability of molybdenum the selectivity to cyclohexanone is increased which otherwise would have been facilitated for dehydration favoring cyclohexene. It is now well established that the surface of mixed oxide catalysts has acidic and basic properties that are reflected in selectivity patterns¹⁵.

Effect of P and B loading :

Fig. 7 compares the catalytic performance of $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3\text{-P}_2\text{O}_5$ (3 wt%) and $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3\text{-B}_2\text{O}_3$

Fig. 5. Effect of % Na_2O loading on the cyclohexanol conversion ($\%C_{\text{CH}}$) and cyclohexanone selectivity ($\%S_{\text{C-none}}$); Calcination temperature : 500 °C. W/F : 86.42 $[\text{g}_{\text{cat}}\text{mol}^{-1}(\text{cyclohexanol})\text{h}]$; Pressure : Ambient.

Fig. 6. Effect of Cs₂O loading on selectivity ratio of cyclohexanone to cyclohexene (S_R C-none/C-ene); Calcination temperature : 500 °C; W/F : 86.42 [g_{cat} mol⁻¹ (cyclohexanol) h]; Pressure : Ambient.

Fig. 7. % Conversion of cyclohexanol on P₂O₅ and B₂O₃ loaded Fe₂O₃-MoO₃ catalyst; Calcination temperature : 500 °C; W/F : 86.42 [g_{cat} mol⁻¹ (cyclohexanol) h]; Pressure : Ambient.

(3 wt%) with Fe₂O₃-MoO₃. The conversion of cyclohexanol increased from 52.13% to nearly complete conversion for Fe₂O₃-MoO₃-B₂O₃ (3 wt%) and that of 61.75% for Fe₂O₃-MoO₃-P₂O₅ (3 wt%) at 230 °C. The introduction of P₂O₅ and B₂O₃ seems not to change the acid-base property of V₂O₅-MoO₃ substantially. Therefore it could not cause the remarkable modification in the catalytic behavior. Thus

Fe₂O₃-MoO₃-P₂O₅ and Fe₂O₃-MoO₃-B₂O₃ kept the characteristics of Fe₂O₃-MoO₃. The cyclohexanone selectivity at lower temperature of 180 °C also shows not much difference.

Conclusion

Anaerobic decomposition of cyclohexanol over alkali metal promoted catalyst leads to dehydrogenation at lower temperature of 180 °C and on further increase in temperature dehydration prevails. The contact time of W/F = 86.42 [g_{cat} mol⁻¹ (cyclohexanol) h] is optimum at ambient pressure. Modification of supported Fe₂O₃-MoO₃ catalyst with alkali salt solutions generated their characteristic phases. Modification with phosphorous and boron does not change the catalysts' acido-basic characteristics substantially as compared to alkali loading and this is reflected in their catalytic performance in cyclohexanol dehydrogenation. The selectivity to desired intermediate (cyclohexanone) is increased by the use of increasingly complex catalyst system formed due to cesium loading.

Experimental

Materials :

NaOH, KOH and CsNO₃ were obtained from Loba Chemie, Thomas Baker and s.d. fine chemicals and used for Na, K and Cs loading respectively. The H₃PO₄ and H₃BO₃ were obtained from Loba Chemie for P and B loading respectively. Cyclohexanol from s.d. fine chemicals was used for catalytic reaction. Ferric nitrate and ammonium molybdate (Loba Chemie, LR) were used for catalyst preparation.

Preparation of Fe-Mo-M-O catalysts :

Preparation of buffer :

Solution A : 0.1 M Na-citrate solution was made by adding 21.04 g citric acid to 200 ml of a 1 N NaOH solution; it was then made up to 1 l. Solution B : 28.2 ml portion of solution A was made up to 100 ml with 0.1 N HCl. This solution B is the buffer having a pH of 1.8.

Preparation of the ferric molybdate catalyst (10 g scale) :

The synthesis was carried out by the coprecipitation

method. One litre of the buffer solution (pH 1.8) prepared as above was placed in a large beaker. Ferric nitrate (15% solution) and ammonium molybdate (30% solution) were separately added dropwise to the buffer (8.3 g of ferric nitrate reacted with 9.0 g of ammonium molybdate). The rate of addition was carefully controlled to maintain the pH of the mixture around 1.8 at room temperature. The precipitate was kept overnight for ageing. The supernatant liquid was decanted and the precipitate was filtered and washed with water till it was free from chloride. The precipitate was dried at 110 °C for 10 h, and then powdered and calcined in air at 390 °C for 15 h. This powder was pelleted, crushed and sieved for further study.

This catalyst was treated as parent catalyst and subsequent loading was carried out over this catalyst with aqueous solutions of NaOH, KOH, H₃BO₃, H₃PO₄, LiNO₃ and CsNO₃ to get Fe-Mo-Na-O, Fe-Mo-K-O, Fe-Mo-B-O, Fe-Mo-P-O, Fe-Mo-Li-O and Fe-Mo-Cs-O catalysts respectively. Loading was carried out independently in a stainless steel tray with addition of aqueous salt solutions of the impregnants slowly with constant stirring. After complete addition, the material was placed on a steam bath for complete evaporation. At intervals, the mixture was stirred so as to get homogeneous impregnation of the support by the active material. After complete evaporation, the material was dried at 110 °C in an oven for 2 h and further calcined stepwise at 200 °C/1 h, 300 °C/1 h, 400 °C/1 h and finally at 500 °C/2 h, to give the final catalyst.

Catalyst characterization :

The samples were thoroughly grounded to fine powder using pestle and mortar and were subjected for XRD investigation. X-Ray diffraction patterns of the samples were recorded using RigakuD_{max}/III VC diffractometer using Ni-filtered CuK α ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) radiation at a scanning rate 4° min⁻¹ in the range 2 $\theta = 10$ –80. Fig. 1 depicts the XRD patterns of Fe₂(MoO₄)₃ (unmodified ferric molybdate) and modified ferric molybdate catalyst samples. Table 1 explains the specification of various phases.

Catalytic reaction :

Vapor phase experiments were performed at at-

mospheric pressure in a fixed bed, vertical, down-flow, integral silica reactor (length 37 cm; i.d. = 12 mm with a thermocouple well of length 14 cm and i.d. = 6 mm) placed inside a double-zone furnace. The powdered catalysts are pressed, pelleted, crushed and sieved to obtain 10–20 mesh particles. 1.5 g of catalyst was charged at the center of the reactor in such a way that the catalyst was sandwiched between the layers of inert porcelain beads. The upper portion of the reactor served as a vaporizer cum pre-heater. All heating and temperature measurements were carried out using 'Aplab' temperature controller and indicator instruments. A thermocouple was positioned at the center of the catalyst bed to monitor the exact temperature of the catalyst. Activation of the catalyst consists of heating in a flow of dry air at the rate of 25 cc min⁻¹ at 500 °C for at least 8 h before each run. The catalyst was then cooled to the desired reaction temperature in the flow of dry nitrogen at 20 cc min⁻¹. The reactant mixture was fed by a syringe pump (ISCO, Model 500D, USA). The products of the reaction were condensed in a receiver using ice cold trap. The used catalyst was recycled by calcining it in the flow of dry air for 10 h prior to use for subsequent reaction at higher temperature.

The liquid products were analyzed by gas-chromatograph (Model HP 5890 series II) equipped with a carbowax column (30 m \times 0.5 mm i.d.) and FID. The products were confirmed by GCMS (Shimadzu GC-17 A and QP-5000 Mass Spectrometer).

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Vyawahare *et al.* : Alkali metal promoted iron-moybdenum oxide as catalysts for anaerobic *etc.*

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